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Studies on the Catalytic Hydration of Cyano-Compounds to Amides

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The amides are generally prepared by the hydration of cyano-compounds. This reaction is catalysed by acids or alkalis in homogeneous phase. This has been reported by several investigators^{1,2}.

The disadvantage inherent in the use of alkalis or mineral acids are the formation of the corresponding carboxylic acids as by products. This results in corresponding decrease in the yield of the amides. Further, the product of such reaction would consist of a solution of a mixture of amides, the acid and the catalyst used which necessitates a rather elaborate separation step.

It should be possible to avoid or to minimise the hydrolytic action by the use of water insoluble cata-

lyst of either acidic or basic nature. With this concept, various metallic oxides like V_2O_5 , MnO_2 , Cr_2O_3 , etc. were tested and were tested and were found to be useful in this connection.

The general procedure for hydration is accomplished by refluxing an aqueous solution of the cyano-compound for 3 to 10 hours in water with a suitable amount of catalyst. After the reaction, the catalyst is filtered off. The catalyst can be reused after proper drying in an air-oven. The filtrate is processed for the separation of cyano-compound and the amide generally by the extraction with ether. The aqueous extract after evaporation yields a solid mass which consists of the crude amide. Similarly, the unreacted cyano-compound is obtained by the evaporation of the ethereal extract. The identity of the amide as well as the cyano-compound is confirmed by I.R. spectroscopy.

Results and Discussions

From Table-1, it is observed that of all the catalysts, manganese dioxide exhibited highest selectivity towards hydration of pyridine carbonitrile to pyridine carboxamide. Therefore exhaustive investigation on different aspects of hydration reaction has been carried out with this catalyst to optimise the yield of pyridine 3-carboxamide and pyridine 4-carboxamide.

Since, the method of the preparation of the catalyst modifies the surface properties which in turn governs the catalytic activity, different methods of preparation of manganese dioxide were adopted and their activities were tested.

From Table 2, it was found that manganese dioxide, prepared by the reduction of $KMnO_4$ with manganous salts, exhibits special properties and characteristics on the catalyst resulting in the highest selectivity of the catalyst.

TABLE-1. COMPARATIVE EFFICIENCY OF DIFFERENT CATALYSTS IN THE HYDRATION OF PYRIDINE CARBONITRILE TO PYRIDINE CARBOXAMIDE

Catalyst	Wt. of cyano-compd. gms.	Solvent cc	Reaction time hr.	Temp. °C	Yield of Amide gms.	Cyano-compd recovered gms.
V_2O_5 (1 gm)	4. C.P. 10 gms.	Water 35 cc.	5	100°	1 gm.	6.3 gm.
MnO_2 (1 gm)	3. C.P. 5 gms.	Water 35 cc	5	100	5.37 gm	-
Cr_2O_3 (1 gm)	3. C.P. 4 gms.	Water 35 cc	5	100	1.3 gm	0.9 gm.

TABLE-2. COMPARATIVE EFFICIENCY OF MnO_2 CATALYST PREPARED BY DIFFERENT METHODS
1 gm. of MnO_2 and 5 gms. of pyridine 3-carbonitrile in each case

Catalyst	Wt. of Pyridine 3-carbonitrile gms.	Water cc.	Residence time hr.	Temp. °C	Yield of Amide gm.	Nitrile recovered gm.
A	5	35	5	100	5.5	Nil
B	5	35	5	100	1.75	1.08
C	5	35	5	100	0.32	2.07
D	5	35	5	100	5.37	nil
E	5	35	5	100	5.7	nil

A- MnO_2 from Mn-acetate + H_2SO_4 + $K_2S_2O_8$

B- MnO_2 from $MnCl_2$, $4H_2O$ + $KMnO_4$.

C- MnO_2 from $Mn(NO_3)_2$ + H_2O heated upto 400°

D- MnO_2 from $KMnO_4$ + $MnCl_2$, $4H_2O$, heated upto 500°. for 3 hours.

E- MnO_2 from $MnSO_4$ + $KMnO_4$.

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